

DEVELOPING ORAL SPEECH IN COMMUNICATION THROUGH DIALOGUE IN TEACHING THE LANGUAGE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10817402>

Abstract. *The oral speech is not easy to master, especially, for foreign languages learners. In fact, in practice, EFL learners often meet complicated problems and difficulties when it comes to perform orally. However, it has been argued that classroom dialogues can stand as a good means and an appropriate instructional strategy that can help EFL learners overcome their problems, and hence, enable these learners become competent and proficient in the target languages. The aim of this study is to investigate the notion of developing oral speech in communication through dialogue.*

Keywords: *EFL learners, dialogue, oral speech.*

Introduction

Nowadays, English language has become the most known foreign language. Learners of English as a foreign language give more attention to develop the oral speech. Thus, they communicate and interact with people. They try to gain the ability to express themselves in the target language. Thus, classroom plays a major role in the process of foreign language learning. In fact, the role of classroom dialogues in learning has become an important factor because it creates opportunities for the classroom community to develop knowledge and skills.

Therefore, classroom dialogues enable the learners to express real life situations, which they can use in their lives. However, expressing the learners personalities in the target language is the essential aim that they are looking for through the learning a foreign language. Learners have to practice English language more specifically in the classroom, with the teachers plan and guidance.

Ostensibly, for learners who study English language in a non-English speaking setting, it is important to experience real communicative situations in which they will learn how to express their own thoughts and opinions. This simply means, very often those learners encounter many oral speech difficulties which usually lead those learners to the lack of oral fluency and the confidence to speak.

Since the majority of EFL learners practice English language only in classrooms, it presents the primary space where learners speak and listen to English language. Dialogues and talk are dynamic way which allow learners to communicate and use the target language as individually or collectively. Through dialogues learners have the opportunity to exchange ideas and views, and also speak language. By this, they will overcome their oral speech difficulties. The aim is to improve the EFL learners' oral speech ability and make them eloquent when presenting oral tasks.

Literature review

EFL learners try to show their proficiency through speaking skill because it enables them to communicate, and express themselves in the target language as a native speaker. Concerning this idea, Celce-Murcia sees ‘that the ability to speak a language is synonymous with knowing that language since discourse is a fundamental means of communication. According to Widdowson, speaking is the active production skill. And, the utilization of the oral production is the capacity of someone to communicate orally with others. Such a believed is shared by

Khamkhien believes in the importance of speaking in foreign language learning. To emphasize on, EFL learners should speak more in the classroom. For many specialists, the speaking skill refers to knowing the language. Here, when the learners speak, they are more able to learn about the EFL rules, structures, pronunciation, and even its pragmatic use. Moreover, being able to speak is being able to read, to write, and even being able to listen. The more learners use utterances and sentences verbally, the more they can read them and understand them, the more they can use them in paragraphs, and the more they can receive them quickly. Hence, since learners speak much more the EFL for communication, they are not passive because they produce words and sentences.

Freire defines a dialogue as a literal and theoretical form consisting of written or spoken conversational exchange between two or more people. Thus, out of this short definition of a dialogue, one may say that dialogues are a way to convey and receive messages between people. They are spoken or written to express what one wants, to say what one thinks about, and to negotiate with others. In other words, dialogues are more felicitous when the participants share certain elements as the linguistic and the cultural background.

From a historical perspective, according to Kramer the practice of education dialogue is at least as old ancient Greek culture. If we reflect on the term dialogue, we see that the Greek prefix “*dia*” has a variety of meanings, including: across, among, through, together. The Greek word “*logos*” has many cognates as well, including: reason, law, truth, word. Thus etymologically, “*dia-logos*” means speaking meaningfully between people”. From this context, a dialogue means something that is done orally for a specific purpose. It is obvious that the use of dialogues in the education enterprise started in the past. This means the use of the dialogues in this enterprise is not a new, but it is more important.

Research methodology

Scholars and English language teachers believe that communicative skills should be developed as much as possible to make EFL learners communicate appropriately in a target language. Albright claims that most learners cannot reach a satisfactory level of proficiency if textbooks do not present materials designed to develop communicative skill. In the same way, Slavin notes that cooperative or collaborative learning is often judged as to increase learners’ academic achievements, self-esteem, and motivation. Thus, using dialogues as a tool of teaching speaking is a supportive way to instruction. As cited in Dawes and Alexander believes that dialogic teaching is:

Collective: teachers and learners address learning tasks together.
Reciprocal: teachers and learners listen to each other, share ideas and consider alternative viewpoints.

Supportive: learners articulate freely and help one another to reach common understandings.

Cumulative: ideas are chained into coherent lines of enquiry.

Purposeful: teachers plan dialogic teaching with particular educational goals in view.

Analysis and results.

Following what is stated above, teaching dialogues is an ideal method where it brings external situations into the classroom. It makes grow on learners thinking and expand their imagination through topics that they discuss. Besides, teaching dialogues may lead EFL learners engage to a practice to listen, and share thoughts of different perspectives, and issues. These ideas are sustained by Stewart who views that dialogues among classroom participants allow for the

integration of new knowledge with what learners already know, which in turn, it leads to generate further understanding and fresh insights. Interaction among learners and teachers can be the most effective triggers of meaningful learning. Hence, using dialogues in the classroom do not only improve the EFL learners' linguistic backgrounds, but also their mental abilities. Moreover, it ameliorates their skills as listening and listening comprehension. Furthermore, for Dawes dialogic teaching intends to explore what learners think, share with their improving ideas, and make them talk through misunderstandings. Through dialogues teachers are engaging with their learners. This makes them discover how they think and create ideas. In brief, it helps teachers give them chance to speak.

Conclusion

Considering the speaking skill, as the major skill for learners for both the teachers and the learners, the answers of the teachers agreed that their learners' level of speaking is average. All the answered teachers are convinced that a dialogue is an effective strategy in teaching speaking because they apply dialogues in their courses. Both the learners and teachers believe that dialogues have huge advantages in improving learners speaking skill and overcome the speaking difficulties. They agreed on that dialogues should be used often with different topics and should be presented in different ways.

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